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**ON THE QUESTION OF REPRODUCIBILITY OF
SCIENTIFIC RESULTS IN PUBLISHED SCIENTIFIC
ARTICLES.**

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Abstract. Many Scientific Papers are retracted because of Data Fabrication and Data Falsification. Many Scientific Papers are also retracted because the reported results cannot be reproduced by other Scientific Researchers working in the same field. Inability to reproduce Scientific Results presupposes that the Scientific Researchers who published the irreproducible results have either made up the results or were incompetent to perform and draw scientific conclusions from the results obtained. Inability to reproduce published results could also be due to incompetence from the part of the Scientific Researchers who are trying to reproduce the published scientific results. How to differentiate from the two is a major issue that can be very costly and damaging to reputations and livelihood.

The problem of reproducibility of scientific results is a major issue that can be costly and can affect the reputation and livelihood of Scientific Researchers concerned. When Fleischmann and Pons [1] declared to the whole world that they had discovered a means

to produce energy by cold fusion, almost everyone who tried to reproduce the experiment could not. It turned out that the experiment in question was flawed because of the lack of proper controls and lack of expertise in measuring neutrons and helium-4. The only evidence that Fleischmann and Pons provided that would support the fusion of deuterium was the generation heat. However, because they did not stir the heavy water, the dissipation of heat was uneven causing them to measure excess heat that was not there. Fleischmann and Pons were not accused of Scientific Misconduct but of incompetence because they did not fabricate or falsify data. In the United States, there is no law against stupidity or incompetence. One can certainly be sued for incompetence or for using the United States Government money to conduct frivolous and useless experiments. The Fleischmann and Pons' debacle would have been avoided if only they had followed a key requirement of scientific norm, Reproducibility. In view of the importance of the reported results, it would have been prudent to first allow the reproduction of their experiments by other Scientific Researchers. If it was available, they could have published a Preprint. But, Fleischmann and Pons were responsible for the ridicule that they received because they agreed to announce their results to the world in a press conference.

The problem of reproducibility of scientific results is one that is faced by every bona fide Scientific Researcher. What does one do when one cannot reproduce a published scientific results. Unfortunately, there are enough out there to destroy the career of a Scientific Researcher. I remember when I was a graduate student, a new Post-Doctoral Researcher had joined the laboratory to continue and extend the work of another Graduate Student on a very promising line of research. After many months of trying very hard, the Post-Doctoral Researcher could not reproduce the work of the Graduate Student who had left. Because I became a friend of the Post-Doctoral Researcher, I voluntarily agreed to let him take part of a research project that I was pursuing. He ended up cannibalizing my work and did not give me any credit for my contribution. The Lab Director was oblivious to the situation and could not care less because he was going to be a senior author irrespective of who performed the work. The Graduate Student whose work could not be reproduced went on to have an average scientific career as if nothing had happened. In a different case, I spent almost one year of my life to the detriment of

my family's welfare to reproduce a published scientific result and could not. In yet another case, I knew that the published scientific results could not be reproduced because I am an expert in the area of research and alerted the Scientific Journal that published the irreproducible results. I was informed by the Scientific Journal in question that they had determined that there was no Data Fabrication and Data Falsification involved (How the Scientific Journal did that is beyond comprehension) and that I should address the matter with the Research Institution. After, I filed a Complaint to the Research Institution, the latter conducted a perfunctory inquiry and concluded that there was no need to conduct a full investigation. The irreproducible results have not been retracted. As discussed in [2], the Research Universities and other Research Institutions are very good at whitewashing instances of Scientific Misconduct and protecting their so called "star performers" and Scientific Researchers who are also part of the senior management.

That above lessons of life taught me that reproducibility of scientific results must be taken very seriously as it can affect the career of a Scientific Researcher in many ways, including non renewal of scientific appointments. Unfortunately, it is a fact of life that most Scientific Researchers live with and are prepared to tolerate. Their survival instinct made them to just move on when they are faced with the inability to reproduce published scientific results. When one is faced with scientific results that are in opposition to one's own scientific results, it is normal that one would want to determine the correctness of a scientific result by trying to repeat a published scientific result. The question is how much time and resources must one devote to such endeavor. The answer is not very clear because it can affect one's career. There is no scientific reward or recognition in trying to show that a published scientific result is irreproducible, especially if one is going against a "famous and powerful" Scientific Researcher. Describing how one's scientific results are at odd with an irreproducible scientific result is also a very delicate one. One's scientific career could take a dive as a result of going against the so called powerful and famous Scientific Researcher (the recent lawsuit filed by Jeannie Lee, an epigeneticist at Harvard Medical School and Massachusetts General Hospital in Boston, against the Howard Hughes Medical Institute and Thomas Cech, a nobel prize winner illustrates the issue [2]). Most review articles that I have read only praise positive scientific results even

if some of these positive scientific results cannot be reproduced. Very few review articles that I have read highlight scientific results that cannot be reproduced or critically assess experimental procedures and interpretation of the scientific results. It is significant that there is a scientific journal, FASEB BioReports that accepts to publish scientific articles that attempt to "reproduce" published scientific articles that cannot be reproduced.

According to a survey by the American Society for Cell Biology [3], a whopping 70% of its members stated that they had tried but were unable to reproduce a the results of a published scientific article. What was quite alarming was that almost 40% of the responders stated that the problem of irreproducibility was not resolved because the irreproducible scientific results were performed by people who lacked expertise and rigor. When asked what factors caused the problems of irreproducibility of published scientific results, almost 48 % agreed that poor laboratory record keeping was a factor, ~39 % agreed that pressure to publish was a factor, ~21 % agreed that poor methodological training was a factor, and ~40% agreed that poor statistical knowledge was a factor. A survey by the Journal Nature [4] described what could be construed as a bombshell. According to that survey, "More than 70% of researchers have tried and failed to reproduce another scientist's experiments, and more than half have failed to reproduce their own experiments". What kind of Scientific Researchers called themselves Scientific Researchers when they cannot even reproduce their own experiments. It is interesting to note that the Journal Nature is the same journal that published the work of Rosalind Franklin on the structure of DNA [5] and the work of Pierre Beneviste on the "memory of water" [6]. While the former work has been reproduced and celebrated (although Rosalind Franklin was not initially recognized as the one who first described the DNA molecule as a helix) the latter has not been reproduced (oddly the paper has not been retracted sua sponte by the Journal Nature).

It is my view that when a scientific result is published, it must be reproducible or the whole foundation of scientific endeavor falls to pieces. There must be zero tolerance for Irreproducible Results. Before an important Scientific Paper is published, the results in it must be reproduced by at least two other independent laboratories. Technology permits

the publication of preprints so that priority is not an issue anymore. Had the papers by Okabata et al. [7] been confirmed prior to publication in the Journal Nature, ridicule and embarrassment for both the authors of the papers and the Journal would have been avoided and many laboratories would not have wasted resources in man/woman hours and dollars trying to reproduce the questionable work. Scientific Journals must also demand that raw data be made available to the whole world to see and analyze as a condition of publication.

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Why was the Scientific Article Entitled "Stimulus-triggered fate conversion of somatic cells into pluripotency" authored by Haruko Okabata et al., and published in Nature [Nature (2014) Vol. 505, pp641-647] retracted.